

Non-Heteroepitaxial CsPbBr₃/Cs₄PbBr₆ Interfaces Results in Non-Passivated Bright Bromide Vacancies

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Abstract:

Metal halide perovskite interfaces and heterostructures are crucial for engineering future technologies based on these new classes of semiconductors. Intensely debated is the structure-function role of the CsPbBr_3 and Cs_4PbBr_6 as mixed phases and their synergistic contribution to emission and efficiency. We show a clear connection between the growth of the competing Cs_4PbBr_6 phase and the presence of Br vacancies, which serve as the growth nucleation sites. Our understanding is fuelled by a unique cryogenic ultra-fast time-resolved cathodoluminescence (TRCL) spectroscopy study of CsPbBr_3 and mixed-phase microcrystals. This method precisely pinpoints the spatial location of emission centers and analyses them spectrally and temporally, unveiling their defect-based origin. Bromide vacancies act as trap states at cryogenic temperatures, resulting in an apparent spectral split easing their detection. We find non-heteroepitaxial growth at the interface of the two phases $\text{CsPbBr}_3/\text{Cs}_4\text{PbBr}_6$ and agglomeration of precipitants that are bromide depleted. Our data connects the under-passivated bromide vacancy states at the interface to enhanced emission from the $\text{CsPbBr}_3/\text{Cs}_4\text{PbBr}_6$ heterostructures.

Introduction:

Understating the structure-function relationship between lead halide perovskites and competing phases is a challenging undertaking.¹ All-inorganic lead halide perovskites (IHPs) are hailed as candidate materials for next-generation light-harvesting solar cells, light-emitting diodes (LEDs), and detectors.^{2,3,4,5,6,7} Cesium lead bromide perovskites are considered for high energy detection due to high spectral resolution and a tunable high-efficiency response, as well as low-temperature processing.^{8,9,10} A working technology warrants an understanding of the influence of secondary phases and interfaces on CsPbBr₃ properties. Halide Perovskite's anti-bonding electronic structure yields a high preference for shallow trap levels formation,^{11,12} which does not hamper emission and results in high photoluminescence quantum efficiency (PLQY). Interestingly, when CsPbBr₃ is coupled with a non-emissive phase,^{13,14} such as Cs₄PbBr₆, significantly enhanced PLQY is measured. Strongly debated, numerous mechanisms have been suggested to explain this mutually increased brightness. Firstly, shallow trap states ($\sim K_B T$ from the band edges) at the interface act as extra luminescent centers and boost PLQY.^{15,16} Secondly, during growth, Cs₄PbBr₆ can act as a host matrix for small CsPbBr₃ nanocrystals with carrier confinement and enhanced PLQY.^{17,18} Finally, surface passivation of CsPbBr₃ by Cs₄PbBr₆,¹⁹ eliminates surface traps and enhances radiative processes. These enhancement mechanisms are not necessarily mutually exclusive and can coexist. This work focuses on samples where the trap-based mechanism is emphasized. In CsPbBr₃ trap-based levels become visible as a spectral split in low temperatures photoluminescence (PL)^{20,21,22}. Indeed, there are alternative explanations for the spectral splitting and linewidth broadening at room temperature, such as an internal emission reabsorption effect.^{23,24} exciton-exciton scattering²⁵, phononic interactions^{26,27}, and Rashba-Dresselhaus effect.^{28,29,30}

Here we show that CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals grown from solution under diffusion-limited conditions (fast growth-short time), spectroscopic signatures of bromide deficiencies are prevalent. This is confirmed with low-temperature ultra-fast cathodoluminescence characterization that enables the correlation of spatial, spectroscopic, and temporal information. Different samples of CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals grown under reaction-limited conditions (longer growth times in the same solution). In such longer processes, the growth of the Cs₄PbBr₆ (Cs-rich) phase on surfaces of CsPbBr₃ microcrystals is dominant. When studying the structural and compositional nature of the interface between the two phases, we find non-epitaxial growth, bromide vacancies, and lead precipitates.²² We hypothesize that these bromide vacancies facilitate the later growth of Cs₄PbBr₆ (Cs-rich) on existing CsPbBr₃ surfaces.

Experimental

Micro-crystals of CsPbBr₃ were synthesized via an anti-solvent approach.^{3,31,32} In our modified synthesis, we added the precursor solution into the anti-solvent in a rapid single addition, which results in the fast nucleation and growth of multiple micro-crystals.

CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals synthesis:

The precursor solution was prepared by dissolving into a 10ml DMSO solution a mixture of 1:1 CsBr (99.999%, Aldrich): PbBr₂(99.999%, Aldrich) powders, for a final concentration of 0.065M. Next, the solution was stirred for 5 hours and then left to rest for 24hrs. Before each use, the precursor solution was stirred for several minutes. To form the micro-crystals, 10 (μ L) DMSO precursor solution was injected (using a pipet) into a 25 (*ml*) glass containing 10 (*ml*) of acetone solution and a submerged substrate at the bottom of the glass. Immediately after the injection, orange color precipitation began to appear and to collect on the substrate (Figure S1 in the supplementary material, SI). To grow the Cs₄PbBr₆ fins, the substrate was left to soak in solution for at least 10 min, while the glass was covered. Longer soak times of 30min resulted in the growth of many fins.

Spectroscopic measurements:

To measure the PL emission originating from the entire sample, micro-crystals that were deposited onto a glass substrate were measured using Synergy H1 hybrid multi-mode reader (BioTek®) spectrometer. The irradiation source was a xenon lamp (Xe900), which produced a 370nm excitation wavelength using interference filters and dichroic mirrors for wavelength specificity and a photomultiplier tube (PMT) detector. A blank substrate was used as a reference for each measurement. To measure the emission from individual micro-crystals, confocal PL measurements were carried using Horiba Jobin Yvon (LabRAM HR Evolution®) microscope attached with a 325 (*nm*) laser with an output of 30 (*mW*). Measurements were carried using a 1% ND filter, X40 objective lens, and 600 (*gr/mm*) grating. To calculate the absorption of the micro-crystals, samples with glass substrate (along with blank reference) were measured integrated sphere system, Cary 5000 UV-VIS-NIR spectrophotometer, which measures the diffuse and specular transmission and reflection using the DRA-2500 (200-2500nm). Low-temperature PL measurements were carried using a home-built system where the sample was excited by a 405 (*nm*) CW laser diode. The laser beam and the resulting emission were focused through a 20X objective (Mitutoyo, M Plan Apo HL) and split by a dichroic mirror (Thorlabs, DMLP425). The emission was sent to a TRIAX 552 spectrometer equipped with liquid nitrogen cooled CCD (Roper Scientific). The sample's stage was cooled down using a cryostat cooled with helium.

Electron microscopy measurements:

SEM-EDS measurements were carried out using an FEI Quanta200 microscope. Samples were placed at 10mm working distance and were measured at an acceleration voltage of 10 (*KV*). SEM-EDS measurements were calibrated by removing the substrate's background signal (Silicon). Known CsPbBr₃ crystal (via TEM, XRD) was used as an internal standard, to identify the CsPb₂Br₅ and Cs₄PbBr₆ phases. High-resolution SEM micrographs were acquired using a Zeiss Ultra-Plus high-resolution SEM (HRSEM). Samples were placed at a working distance of 3mm and measured using acceleration voltages between 1-1.5 (*KV*). CL and TRCL measurements were conducted on an Allalin Chronos instrument from Attolight. In this tool, a focused electron beam scans the sample while the optical emission is collected and analysed by a spectrometer, enabling the

simultaneous acquisition of secondary electron (SE) and CL colorized band micrographs. The spectrometer consists of a 320 (mm) focal length, monochromator (Horiba iHR320) fitted with a high-speed UV-Vis CDD camera (Andor Newton 920) for CL measurement and a streak camera (Hamamatsu C10910) for TRCL measurements. The CL spectra and the colorized band micrographs were acquired with a beam energy of 3 (KV). During TRCL measurements, the electron beam was pulsed at 80 (MHz) with energy of 6 (KV) using a laser-focused on the Schottky field emission gun (FEG). The sweep circuit of the streak camera is synchronized with the electron beam pulses with a synchro scan unit. A cryogenic nano positioning stage allows to vary the sample temperature from 10 to 300 (K). Site-specific lamellas for the TEM measurements were prepared using Ga⁺ Focused Ion Beam (FIB) type FEI Helios NanoLab DualBeam G3 UC. In the beginning, the region of interest was covered by a protective Pt layer, followed by the lift-out procedure at 30kV. Lamellae thinning was performed at the accelerating voltages of 30 and 5 (kV) up to the final thickness of 70 (nm). The TEM measurements were first conducted using a Thermo Fisher/FEI Tecnai G2 T20 S-Twin LaB TEM operated at 200 (KeV), with a 1Kx1K Gatan 694 slow-scan CCD. High-resolution imaging, diffraction patterns acquisition, and chemical mapping were done in a Thermo Fisher/FEI Titan-Themis double Cs-corrected HR-S/TEM, operated at 300 (kV) and equipped with a Ceta2 4Kx4K camera (for TEM mode) and a Bruker Dual-X EDX detectors for STEM-EDX chemical mapping. The high-resolution STEM micrographs were acquired using a high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) STEM detector with a collection angle range of 93-200 (mRad) and beam convergence of 21 (mRad). The STEM-EDX measurement were acquired and analysed using the Thermo Fisher Velox software.

X-ray diffraction:

We used a Rigaku Smart-Lab 9 kW high-resolution X-ray diffractometer, equipped with a rotating anode X-ray source Using theta-2theta mode and in-plane mode, with radiation of $\lambda = 1.5418$ (Å) (Cu K α), angular range of $2\theta = 10^\circ - 70^\circ$ with a step size of 0.01°.

Results and discussion

The “short” reaction time and lack of stirring resulted in diffusion-limited growth and yielded pristine CsPbBr₃ micro-crystals (Figure S1 in the SI). EDS measurements (Figure S2 and Table S1 in the SI) showed the constituents’ expected (within error) atomic ratio. XRD and TEM measurements further confirm the structure is CsPbBr₃ (orthorhombic) phase with negligible amounts of by-products such as Cs-rich phase (e.g., peak $2\theta = 31.01^\circ$) (Figure S6 in the SI) and CsPb₂Br₅ (Pb-rich) phase, which is morphologically distinct and grows as macroscopic thin sheets onto the substrate (Figure S4 and Table S3 in the SI).

Figure 1 Characterization of mixed phases microcrystals containing $\text{CsPbBr}_3/\text{Cs}_4\text{PbBr}_6$ interfaces. (a) Absorption and emission spectra were taken from the entire macroscopic sample containing many crystals. Inset: extraction of Urbach energy through the relation $\alpha = \alpha_0 \exp\left(\frac{h\nu}{E_U}\right)$, here α is the absorption coefficient, α_0 is a constant, $h\nu$ is the photon energy and E_U is the Urbach energy. (b) XRD patterns with identification markers of deposited LHP particles on a glass substrate left for 30 min in the solution. CsPbBr_3 (ICDD 04 – 014 – 9676), Cs_4PbBr_6 (ICDD 04 – 015 – 9683) and CsPb_2Br_5 (ICDD 00 – 054 – 0753) phases are detected. (c) SEM micrograph of “long growth” micro-crystals. Marked in green are Cs_4PbBr_6 (Cs-rich) fin-like morphologies which grow on the micro-crystals. (d, e) Close-up micrograph on a fin depicting a rough surface, the triangular shaped inclusion are we hypothesized to be CsPbBr_3 .

We then tested a variation of the synthesis in which long growth times are tested and micro-crystals are left in solution for more than 10 minutes. We discovered that this would noticeably change the morphology and photoluminescence of the crystals. After long growth, the sample displays a significant increase in emission, apparent also for the naked eye. Structurally different are distinct fin-shaped crystals that grow on the facets of the perovskite crystals (see scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs in Figure 1, c, d). These structures were identified as a competing Cs_4PbBr_6 phase via XRD (Figure 1 b) and EDS measurements (Figure S3 and Table S2 in the SI). We, therefore, refer to these as mixed-phase micro-crystals samples, in which the

Cs_4PbBr_6 phase grows at a later stage, typically on CsPbBr_3 surfaces. High-resolution SEM imaging shows Cs_4PbBr_6 fins present a rough surface (Figure 1 d), at times with triangular shapes hypothesized as CsPbBr_3 inclusions (Figure S5 in the SI), which may explain the ongoing conundrum in the assignment of emission to Cs_4PbBr_6 ^{44,45} and many more studies not cited for brevity.

We now use HRTEM to verify the crystal and interfaces structure with spatial atomic resolution. High-quality, micro-crystal lamella was prepared via a Focused Ion Beam (FIB). Electron diffraction patterns show that the micro-crystals are not single crystals but comprise two lattice planes with $[\bar{1}\bar{1}0]$ and $[001]$ zone axes (Figure S8 in the SI). Microcrystals polycrystallinity sits well with the rapid growth of the CsPbBr_3 crystals. We find no evidence for the existence of Cs-rich grains residing in the micro-crystals of pristine CsPbBr_3 .

We then selected mixed-phase samples to prepare TEM lamella comprising the interface region between the CsPbBr_3 and the Cs_4PbBr_6 phases. High angle annular dark-field scanning TEM (HAADF-STEM) micrographs of the two phases (Figure 2 a, b) show a clear phase contrast between the two sides of the interface. EDS measurements from each phase match the expected values (within instrument error) (Figure S9 and Table S4 in the SI). The most surprising and interesting observation came from EDS compositional interface mapping. Our analysis shows a significant concentration of lead-enriched precipitates (Figure 2 d). We have used a comparative approach in which EDS line scans in the same image are compared and used as an internal standard. From this analysis, it is apparent the interface shows an increase in the lead count and a decrease in bromide content, while the cesium level remains the same as in the host phase (Figures 2 e, f, h, i). We hypothesize that during the formation of Cs_4PbBr_6 , lead diffuses from the CsPbBr_3 towards the interface due to a concentration gradient between the phases and the need to maintain charge neutrality at the interface. With time we observe coarsening of lead particles at the interface. We hypothesize this further contributes to a bromide depleted interface from charge balance considerations. Strong support for this hypothesis comes from the orientation relation at the interface. TEM diffractograms of the CsPbBr_3 and Cs_4PbBr_6 phases are consistent with zone axes $[\bar{1}03]$ and $[\bar{2}\bar{1}0]$ respectively (Figures S10, S11 in the SI). The interface between the two phases has a high-index non-heteroepitaxial nature suggests that Cs_4PbBr_6 growth nucleates on pre-existing defects, namely bromide vacancies. Perovskites are known for their sensitivity to electron beam. For our samples we conducted a long TEM exposure measurement and ruled out beam-related desorption of bromide^{35,36,37,38} (see Video V1). In some experiments we do see electron beam-induced void formation⁴⁸ black areas in Figure 2 a and the area marked by a green box in Figure 2 b) and were careful not to include these in our analysis.

Figure 2 HAADF-STEM and EDS analysis of the CsPbBr₃/Cs₄PbBr₆ interface. (a) HAADF-STEM micrograph depicting the interface between the two phases. (b) BF-HRTEM micrograph of the interface. Marked blue is the interface line, in red are the lead enriched precipitants, and in green a void within the Cs₄PbBr₆ phase. (c) HAADF-STEM micrograph magnified on the interface area. (d-g) Interface EDS maps depict elemental concentrations of lead, bromide, cesium, and platinum. (h) Combined EDS map of all mentioned elements. Marked with an arrow is the acquisition of the line scan (i) Plot result of the EDS line scan starting in the Cs₄PbBr₆ phase and ending in the CsPbBr₃ phase.

Baranov et al. claimed heteroepitaxial relation between the two above phases.³⁴ However, this report and others made on nanoscale systems,^{42,43} are for the colloidal transformation of CsPbBr₃ from Cs₄PbBr₆ nanocrystals. Nanocrystals surfaces are highly passivated with organic ligands and therefore with lower surface energy from the micro-crystals in this report. This example and many others demonstrate that the nature of the perovskite-Cs-rich interface is highly dependent on growth conditions.

We now connect the structure of CsPbBr₃ and its interface with the underlying electronic properties through temperature dependence photoluminescence and cathodoluminescent studies. A pristine CsPbBr₃ sample was cooled to ~10K and gradually heated to ~100K in a home-built PL microscope setup enabling excitation of individual micro-crystal with minimal drift. At ~10K, the emission spectrum presents three peaks at 535 (peak 1), 540 (peak 2), and 542 nm (peak 3) (Figure S13 a in the SI). Additionally, a wider and weaker emission at ~546-550 nm is attributed to the emission of donor-acceptor pairs.³⁹ As the temperature decreases, the three peaks are red-shifted as expected^{22,27,40} (inset of Figure S13 a). To determine the nature of the different peaks, power dependence PL measurements were performed⁴¹ at ~13K (Figure S13 b in the SI). We find the intensity of all peaks fits a power law (inset of Figure S13 b) $I \sim L^K$ where L is the excitation power density, I the peak intensity, and K the scaling order, we obtained $1 < K < 2$ for the three peaks, and assign them as band edge, free and bound excitons respectively, see SI for more details.

We now want to spatial pinpoint the origin of these different emissions and check if they are related to specific morphology. For that, we use Cathodoluminescence (CL), an effective method for characterizing localized states in lead halide perovskites.⁴⁷ The pristine micro-crystals were scanned by continuous-wave cathodoluminescence (CWCL) at 10K (Figure 3). In the SI, we bring spectrally selected scans at ~535 nm corresponding to peak 1 and ~540 nm, similar to peaks 2 and 3 found in the low-temperature PL measurements (Figure S13).

A hyperspectral image representation is shown in Figure 3 a, where it is apparent that the 540 nm emission (blue color) is localized while the 535 nm emission is more evenly spread. We, therefore, attributed the 540 nm peak to defect-bound excitons. Indeed, bromide vacancies are

consistent with such peak assignment as observed in the PL study. We now focus on two points in the sample (marked spot 1,2) and present their spectra in Figure 3 b.

For completeness, we mention an additional broad weak peak at ~ 560 nm we observed (Figure S15 in the SI). We assign this to the donor-acceptor emission detected only at low temperatures. Time-resolved cathodoluminescence (TRCL) is now used to better understand exciton dynamics in our samples. TRCL is particularly challenging since it requires an ultra-short (Picosecond) pulse of electrons to generate carriers locally. The generated luminescence is characterized by a streak camera leading to spatially, spectrally, and temporally resolved signals. This unique setup enabled ultrafast CL lifetime spatial mapping of our sample with nm resolution at cryogenic temperatures, 10K. We now examine the spectrally different spots 1 and 2, for their exciton dynamics. Streak camera data of spot 1 (Figure 3 c) is compared to spot 2 (Figure 3 d). While spot 1 shows 535 nm narrow emission and a decay tail (see the spectrally averaged decay curve in Figure 3 e). Spot 2 is spectrally broader around 540 nm and consists of two peaks with different decay curves. The CL lifetime decay curves integrated at around 535 nm and around 540 nm are displayed in Figure 3 f. (Table 1 presents the fitted lifetime data). All decay curves show a dominant fast component and a smaller contribution from a slower component. At spot 1, the fast component accounts for 87% of the intensity and is characterized by a lifetime $\tau_1 = 25.3$ ps while the slower component is characterized by $\tau_2 = 180.3$ ps (Figure 3c). For spot 2, the story is different, while for 535 nm emission, the lifetime is very similar to those at spot 1. ($\tau_1 = 22.9$ ps, $\tau_2 = 153.1$ ps), consistent with band-edge recombination. The lifetime for 540 nm is longer ($\tau_1 = 52.0$ ps, $\tau_2 = 346.5$ ps) compared to the 535 nm range and τ_1 has a smaller contribution (Table 1).

For interpretation of the TRCL, we correlate the data with hyperspectral mapping. It is evident that 540 nm (defect) emission originates from local points on CsPbBr₃ perovskite's edges and corners while the 535 (band-edge) emission is more widespread and less correlated to a morphological feature. (Figure 3g). Another proof for the above assignment comes from the comparison of cryogenic and room temperature TRCL on pristine CsPbBr₃. At room temperature (Figure 4 a, b, c). We measure broader emission spectra as expected but very fast lifetimes $\tau \sim 25$ ps contrary to the cryogenic extended lifetimes. We thus hypothesize that under our working conditions (see experimental), the fast component is related to the radiative band-edge recombination (RR), and the slower components involve some non-radiative interaction possibly Auger recombination (AR), and trap assisted (TA) recombination (see scheme in Figure 4 d). The important lesson from this data is that under CL conditions, the red-shifted, slower emission which is typically localized is observable only at cryogenic temperatures, probably due to thermal equilibrium with the band-edge. All the signs point toward defect emission from the bromide vacancies.

We now study the mixed-phase micro-crystals samples with CL. Figure 5 b, c clearly shows the difference between CsPbBr₃ and Cs₄PbBr₆ (fins). Measured integrated CL intensity from the fins

is two orders of magnitude lower compared to the CsPbBr_3 perovskite for 540nm (defect emission). Nevertheless, we still detect emissions with significantly lower intensities at 377 nm and 650 nm. The filtered CL maps clearly show anticorrelation to CsPbBr_3 band edge emission (e.g., black areas in Figure 5b appear bright in Figure 5d, e). The most important observation here is the very intense and localized emission from CsPbBr_3 inclusions located on Cs_4PbBr_6 fins. (Marked as #3 in Figure 5 b, c) This emission is orders of magnitude brighter than neighbouring CL at point #2 on Cs_4PbBr_6 fins. We assign this enhancement of emission to the presence of emissive states between the two phases, and to the band alignment of energy levels at the interface. Excitons generated in the wide bandgap Cs_4PbBr_6 fins are funneled to the CsPbBr_3 interface to recombine radiatively. The previously discussed under-passivated bromide vacancy at the interface contributes to this enhanced emission.

Figure 3 Low temperatures $\sim 10\text{K}$, CL and TRCL measurement of CsPbBr_3 micro-crystal clusters (a) colorized bands micrograph, using band ranges from (b). (b) CL spectra at spots 1 and 2. Marked with colored rectangles are the band filters used in the mapping of (a). (c, d) Streak camera images acquired at 10 K for (c) spot 1, (d) spot 2. (e, f) Extracted TRCL spectra for (e) spot 1, (f) spot 2. On (f) time evolutions in the 530-533nm and 538-541nm ranges were extracted separately. The ranges are marked as dashed white lines in (d). (g) Illustration of the experiment with band edge and defect-based emissions from different regions along the CsPbBr_3 perovskite's surface.

Figure 4 Room temperature, CL and TRCL measurement of pristine CsPbBr_3 micro-crystal (a) CL streak camera data are taken from a micro-crystal. (b, c) Normalized CL spectra and TRCL, marked by points, and the fitted data (Gaussian for CL and exponential decay function for TRCL) are marked by lines. Extraction of curves from streak data is marked by horizontal and vertical white dashed lines in (a). (d) Schematic of possible relaxation pathways, with the measured lifetimes. slower emission is observable only at cryogenic temperatures, probably due to thermal equilibrium with the band-edge. Trap-assisted TA, radiative band-edge recombination (RR), non-radiative Auger recombination (AR).

Figure 5 Room temperature CL measurement of mixed-phase micro-crystal (a,b) Correlation of SEM/CL image of CsPbBr₃ and intergrown Cs₄PbBr₆ fins. (b) CL hyperspectral image of the cluster, showing dark no emission from the fins compared to bright perovskites. (c) Log scale CL spectrum of selected points on the micro-crystal (d, e) bandpass filters of the hyperspectral at 377,650 nm, respectively, showing opposite behavior with bright emission from the fins compared to no emission of perovskites.

Table 1. TRCL at 10K results summary

Spot#	Wavelength range (nm)	A1	A2	τ_1 (ps)	τ_2 (ps)
1	528.9 - 538.2	0.87	0.13	25.3	183.3
2	533	0.94	0.06	22.9	153.1
2	538 - 541	0.87	0.13	52.0	346.5

Conclusions

We thus conclude, that emissive bromide vacancies in CsPbBr₃, act as nucleation sites for the growth of the non-emissive Cs₄PbBr₆ phase. We showed that the interface has a high concentration of lead-enriched precipitants that are poor in bromide, illustrating that bromide deficiencies take a central part in the emissive properties of the two phases interface. The intermixed nature of CsPbBr₃/ Cs₄PbBr₆ which differ structurally and electronically is resolved through spectroscopic and cathodoluminescence measurements. We highlighted the importance of a time-resolved technique that pinpointed the slower lifetime regions and showed they are red-shifted and localized. The finding supports the hypothesis that bromide vacancies trap states add extra luminescent centers to the interface of Cs₄PbBr₆ and CsPbBr₃. Such observation is an important step in understanding and developing processes for controlled growth of functional interfaces of CsPbBr₃.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors.

Competing

The authors declare no competing interests.

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